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**Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II)
Complexes of 2-(Phenylazo)-
2-cyanoethylethanoate**

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COUPLING of diazonium salts with β -ketonitriles have been studied extensively because the products have found use as yellow dyes and pigments¹⁻³. Transition metal complexes of these azo dyes are reported to have excellent fastness properties¹. However, there appears no systematic investigation on the structural aspects of these azo compounds and their metal complexes. The present communication reports the syntheses and characterisation of 2-(phenylazo)-2-cyanoethylethanoate (phenylazoethylcyanoacetate) and its copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes.

Experimental

Phenylazoethylcyanoacetate was prepared as reported¹. For preparing metal complexes, an aqueous solution (10 ml) of the metal(II) acetate (1 mmol) was added to a stirred solution (50 ml) of the ligand (0.434 g, 2 mmol) in methanol. Sodium acetate was then added to maintain the pH of the mixture at 7-8. The solution was heated on a water-bath for ~1 h, concentrated to ~25 ml and cooled to room temperature. The resulting precipitated complex was filtered, washed successively with very dilute acetic acid (10 ml) and water, and recrystallised from hot ethanol.

Molar conductance of the complexes in ethanol (10^{-3} M) was measured on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Magnetic measurements were made on a Gouy balance and corrected for diamagnetic contribution. Uv-visible spectra were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss DMR 21 spectrophotometer, ir spectra ($4000-200$ cm^{-1}) on a Pye-Unicam SP 3-300

spectrometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian EM 360L spectrometer. C, H, N and the metal content were done by standard methods.

Results and Discussion

All the metal complexes are non-conducting (sp. cond. $< 10 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$) and do not contain the anion of the metal salt used for their preparation. The analytical and physical data are given in Table 1.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL
DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	M p. °C	Colour	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
				C	H	N	Metal
[CuL ₂]	350	Green	1.92	53.25 (53.27)	4.20 (4.40)	16.50 (16.95)	12.80 (12.82)
[CoL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	355	Grey	5.12	53.52 (53.77)	3.92 (4.07)	16.80 (17.11)	11.91 (12.01)
[NiL ₂]	225	Red	—	53.25 (53.80)	3.92 (4.05)	16.85 (17.11)	11.43 (11.96)

Characterisation of ligand: Arylazo derivatives of β -ketonitriles can exhibit azo-hydrazone tautomerism¹. On the basis of uv, ir and ¹H nmr spectral data phenylazoethylcyanoacetate can be represented as **1a**. Thus, the uv spectra of the compound show a broad band (λ_{max} 355 nm) characteristic of the hydrazone tautomer⁴. The ir spectra show a strong band at 2 230 cm^{-1} assignable to the stretching of the cyano group⁵. Characteristic band of ester carbonyl at 1 700-1 800 cm^{-1} is absent. Instead, a strong band at 1 685 cm^{-1} and a medium intensity band at 1 615 cm^{-1} are revealed the former assigned to the stretching of hydrogen bonded ester carbonyl and the latter to C=N stretch of the hydrazone form⁵⁻⁷. In conformity with the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded structure, the spectra display a considerably broad band at 2 800-3 400 cm^{-1} . The absence of a methylene proton signal of the β -ketonitrile moiety and the presence of a low field one-proton signal at δ 12.95 in the ¹H nmr spectra clearly indicate that the compound exists in the hydrogen bonded hydrazone form^{8,9}. Signals due to CH₃, OCH₃ and phenyl groups are observed respectively at δ 1.25 (t), 4.30 (q) and 7.50 (m).

M = Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II}

Characterisation of metal complexes: The uv absorption band of the ligand remained almost unchanged in the spectra of the metal complexes. It is, therefore, evident that no structural alteration of the ligand occurred during complexation. In the ir spectra of the metal complexes, the strong band of the ligand at $2\ 230\text{ cm}^{-1}$ remained almost unchanged in position and intensity. This indicates the absence of any bond formation between the metal ion and the cyano function of the ligand. The band at $1\ 685\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to hydrogen bonded ester carbonyl of the ligand disappeared in the spectra of the metal complexes. Instead, a new band appeared at $\sim 1\ 655\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of all the metal complexes. This band can be assigned to the stretching of the metal bonded carbonyl group⁹. The absence of the broad band of the ligand at $2\ 800\text{--}3\ 400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of complexes, indicate the replacement of the NH proton by the metal ion as in structure 1b. Weak bands at $\sim 3\ 050$ (aromatic C-H) and $\sim 2\ 850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (aliphatic C-H) are also observed in the spectra of all the metal chelates. In the spectra of the cobalt(II) complex a broad band is observed at $3\ 590\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to its coordinated water. Ir spectra of all the metal complexes showed a medium intensity band at ~ 550 (M-N) and a band at $\sim 420\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (M-O)⁶.

Further evidence for the bonding mode of the ligand is provided by the ¹H nmr spectra of the diamagnetic nickel(II) complex. Thus, the low-field signal of the ligand at $\delta 12.95$ disappeared in the spectra of the complex, which indicates the replacement of the NH proton during metal chelation. Thus, the ir and ¹H nmr spectra strongly support the monobasic bidentate nature of the ligand, leaving the cyano function free as in 1b.

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Coordination Complexes of Chromium(III), Manganese(II), Iron(III), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) with some Tri-, Tetra- and Hexadentate Schiff Bases

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THE present paper reports a series of eighteen complexes of Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with the Schiff base ligands *N*-mono(thiophene-2-aldene)-ethylenedimine (L₁), *N,N*-bis(thiophene-2-aldene)-ethylenedimine (L₂) and *N*¹,*N*⁴-bis(thiophene-2-aldene)triethylenetetramine (L₃).

Analytical, conductance, magnetic moment and spectral data were explored to elucidate their structure.

Experimental

Synthesis of ligands: The ligands were prepared by reacting the corresponding carbonyl compound with ethylenediamine in 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 molar ratio, while with triethylenetetramine in 2 : 1 ratio only. The isolated ligands were characterised on the basis of analysis, molecular weight, ir and ¹H nmr spectral data (Table 1).

Synthesis of complexes: The metal salt (0.01 mole) was suspended in methanol (25 ml) and refluxed with the corresponding ligand (0.01 mol) for 6 h. The complexes were crystallised out from the resulting clear viscous solution by repeated treatment with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°). The analytical and physical data of the compounds are given in Table 2.